

PARALLELS AND REFERENCES TO THE WORKS OF CONTEMPORARY AUTHORS IN THE WORKS OF MARCEL PAGNOL

Rahmonkulova Dilafruz Azimovna

Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages
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Annotation: This article has been prepared based on a study devoted to the problem of transmitting cultural context when translating a work of fiction. The study is based on two accompanying works of fiction authored by Marcel Pagnol.

Key words: famous, historian, critic, success, cinema.

Born in 1895 in the city of Aubagne, 20 km east of Marseille, in the family of a school teacher, Joseph Pagnol, and a seamstress, Augustine (née Lanso). Later, with two younger brothers and a sister, the whole family moved to Marseille. Already at the age of sixteen, Marcel, together with his friends, founded the magazine "Fortunio", along with this, a group of his like-minded people staged theatrical performances. In 1910 his mother dies, and in 1912 his father marries again. In 1913, Marcel entered the University of Aix-en-Provence and began literary activity; a year later he was drafted to the front of the First World War, and in January 1915 he was declared unfit for military service. In 1916, Marcel Pagnol married against his father's will and left for Paris, where he worked as an English teacher until 1927. In the capital, he met young writers, and together with Paul Nivois in 1924 he wrote the play "Merchants of Fame." Success came to him only after the play "Topaz", created in 1928. From 1925 to 1938 he was married to actress Oran Demazi; in 1933, the couple had a son, Jean-Pierre Burgard. In the 1930s, having created a film company, he filmed a trilogy about Marseille workers ("Marius" (1931), "Fanny" (1932) and "César" (1936)), based on his own plays, and also released two versions of "Topaz" "Marius" was produced by Paramount and filmed by Alexandre Korda in the town of Joinville (French: Joinville, Haute-Marne). Fanny, directed by Marc Allegret in Biancourt, was produced by Pagnol himself in collaboration with Établissements Braunberger-Richebé, and César, the only one of the three films whose script was written specifically for film production, was produced by Les Films Marcel Pagnol" without any outside help and filmed by Pagnol himself in his own studio pavilions in Marseille and on location in the outskirts of the city.

In 1934, the film Angèle was released, based on the novel by Jean Giono. Considering Pagnol's increased skill, already in 1934 the famous historian and film critic Henri Agel wrote: "Today, Marcel Pagnol is probably the most intelligent man in French cinema." In 1938, the film "The Baker's Wife" was released, which had some success. In 1940, the film "The Digger's Daughter" became a notable event, and in 1946, "Nais". In 1948, he made the color film "The Beautiful Miller's Wife," and in 1951, the third version of "Topaz." Pagnol's last film work was Letters from My Mill, based on the stories of Alphonse Daudet (1954).[4] In 1955 he headed, and in 1957 and 1966 he was a member of the jury of the Cannes Film Festival[5]. In 1946, he married for the second time the actress Jacqueline Bouvier (1920-2016), whom he directed in six of his films. Marcel Pagnol wrote several essays, as well as an autobiographical novel "Childhood Memories" (fragmentarily published

in Russian under the title "Marcel's Childhood"), consisting of 4 parts: "The Glory of My Father", "My Mother's Castle", "Time of Secrets" " and "It's time for love." The first two parts were started in 1955 and published in 1957, the third part in 1960. The fourth, unfinished part, was published after the author's death, in 1977. The novel is dedicated to Pagnol's childhood years (approximately 1903-1910), spent in Marseille and outside the city, at the New Estate villa. In 1990, "The Glory of My Father" and "The Castle of My Mother" were filmed by director Yves Robert. The playwright and director died in Paris on April 18, 1974. This article was prepared from a study devoted to the problem of transmitting cultural context when translating a work of fiction. The study is based on two works of fiction written by Marcel Pagnol (1895-1974): "The Glory of my Father. My mother's castle" (The Glory of my father. My mother's castle) [5]. Marcel Pagnol is a French playwright and director, born in 1895 in the town of Aubagne, 20 km east of Marseille, in the family of a teacher and seamstress [3]. These factors of his biography justify the cultural and lexical content of the two books, which we considered and analyzed in our scientific work. They are the first to be translated and published in Russian, notably by Pierre Louis Baccheretti and Tatyana Chugunova in 2018 [4]. Both books were written between 1955 and 1957. are autobiographical and consist of a story about the author's childhood in Provence: about national and regional characteristics, both with regard to daily life and his way of life, than the lexical component, this is the reason why these works are rich in unique semantic units, many of which even do not have analogues in the Russian language. Based on this, we decided to study the issue of translating lexical units that are both non-equivalent and simply difficult to translate, and to examine both versions of the texts: original and translated, in order to analyze the work done by the translators. The objectives of the study included the selection of lexical units and their distribution into semantic groups. When analyzing the work, we selected 138 lexical units, some of which were grouped into semantic groups, based on the classification of S. Vlahov and S. Florin [1]. Each is based on a specific context. Here are some examples: Historical context. Examples of lexical units that we include in this group are: Teutobochus barbarians - Teutobod barbarians; The Sioux - Indian - Sioux (Indian people of the Sioux group of the northern United States and southern Canada, who became stereotypical North American Indians); The Apache - Apache (collective name of several culturally related tribes of North American Indians). Political context: Sub-prefectures - sous-prefecture (in France the administrative center of the district) in Russia - sous-prefecture; Religious context: Anticlericals - atheists (anticlericals); Colored figurines - saints (painted figures of saints); Christmas cribs - nativity scene (in the den); Go to mass - receive communion (mass - Catholic mass) (communion is an Orthodox ritual, which consists of consecrating bread and wine in a special way and their subsequent consumption); Curés - priest (in France: Catholic priest); Cups - communion cups Articles of clothing and everyday life: A small muslin toque - muslin cap (muslin) (Kiseinaya young woman is a phraseological unit of the Russian language.

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